

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE ADOPTION OF E-WALLETS AMONG THE SHS FACULTY: A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN GENERATION X AND GENERATION Y

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ABSTRACT

While there are already numerous studies that have determined the factors that influence Generation X and Generation Y to adopt e-wallets respectively, this research is particularly relevant. The research aims to compare the level of influence each of those factors have on Generation X and Generation Y. This research is crucial as it distinguishes any significant differences in the level of influence perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and social influence have on Generation Y and Generation X of the SHS faculty when it comes to their adoption of e-wallets. The study adopted a quantitative comparative research design, which involved gathering a sample of 100 respondents consisting of the SHS faculty members using a simple random technique. Data collection was done by distributing survey questionnaires through Google Forms, and the data collected was then treated to statistical analysis using the Mann-Whitney U Test. The results indicate that Generation X and Y of the SHS faculty have the same level of perception of e-wallets according to their ease of use, usefulness, and social influence. To future researchers who may wish to expand on this specific topic of study, a more extensive and diverse sample is recommended to yield more valid and accurate results.

Keywords: *Perceived ease of use, Perceived usefulness, social influence, E-wallet adoption, Generation X, Generation Y*

INTRODUCTION

An e-wallet is a tool that allows its users to make digital transactions using any gadget or online service (Phophalia et al., 2018). Many businesses today have innovated their payment or transaction methods, evolving from cash to electronic payments, which has led to a rise in Fintech users adopting e-wallets as their primary mode of payment (Halim et al., 2020).

Generation Y (those born between 1981 and 1996) are reported to be among the heavier users of e-wallets, along with Generation Z (Badri, 2020), because of their high willingness to utilize technology in their activities. Meanwhile, Generation X was born between 1965 and 1980 (Rosa et al., 2022), making up the smallest percentage of e-wallet users (JakPat, 2018). Numerous studies have concluded that different factors influence either Generation X or Generation Y into adopting e-wallets, the most mentioned being perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and social influence (Bautista, 2020; Daragmeh et al., 2021; Koleseni & Mandari, 2017; Malik & Annuar, 2021; Yulianita, 2018). However, these studies have failed to focus on the significant differences in the level of influence each of those factors have on Generation X and Generation Y. Thus, the purpose of this study is to compare the level of influence each factor has on Generation X and Generation Y of the SHS faculty.

The study aimed to determine the differences between the factors that influence e-wallet adoption between Generation X and Generation Y of the faculty of SHS. The study's scope explicitly compares the level of influence perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and social influence have on Generation X and Y of the SHS faculty. Full-time, part-time, and tenured teachers participated since the researchers believed they could provide richer insights based on their different experiences. The study, however, excluded the faculty who were not in Senior High School nor part of Generation X or Generation Y.

The study adopted the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Fred Davis developed this theory in 1989 when modern technology first started. TAM explains why individuals adopt different information systems and technology in a work context. It also states that users' behavioral intentions predict their acceptance of technology and that their behavioral intentions are determined by perceived usefulness and ease of use (Davis, 1989).

Research Questions

Because there was a noticeable lack of studies on the significant differences between Generation X and Generation Y in terms of the factors that influence them to adopt e-wallets, the study was conducted to determine the important differences between factors influencing the SHS Faculty Generation X and Generation Y to adopt e-wallets.

The following are the study's sub-questions:

1. What are the demographic profiles of the SHS Faculty Generation X and Generation Y in terms of:
 - A. Age
 - B. Gender
 - C. Working Status
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of influence *perceived ease of use* has on the SHS Faculty Generation X and Generation Y in terms of their intention to adopt e-wallets?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of influence *perceived usefulness* has on the SHS Faculty Generation X and Generation Y in terms of their intention to adopt e-wallets?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of influence *social influence* has on the SHS Faculty Generation X and Generation Y in terms of their intention to adopt e-wallets?

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quantitative comparative research approach. The period for data collection was from November 2023 to April 2024. The primary means of data collection was through online surveys (via Google Forms), which were answered face-to-face and through e-mails.

The study drew its data from one of the universities in U-belt Manila, Philippines, SHS faculty, a population of 232 members. To ensure statistical validity, the research required a sample of 100 respondents, a universally accepted sample size. The researchers employed a simple random sampling technique to gather quantitative data.

The researchers composed their self-made survey questionnaire for data collection. To test for validity, the survey questionnaire underwent a validity test. Furthermore, the reliability of the questionnaire was also tested through a pilot study and computation of the Cronbach Alpha per variable: perceived ease of use ($\alpha = 0.921734$), perceived usefulness ($\alpha = 0.9132327$), and social influence ($\alpha = 0.9382597$). Prior to data gathering, the researchers obtained a permit to conduct the study from the Research Ethics Committee. The researchers used descriptive and inferential statistical analysis, the Mann-Whitney U Test to be specific, to analyze the collected data and draw conclusions about the subject population.

Additionally, the faculty respondents were required to be part of either Generation X, those born between 1965 and 1981 (43-58 years old in 2023), or Generation Y, born

between 1981 and 1996 (28-42 years old in 2023). Those who did not fit the required age range were excluded as respondents.

RESULTS

1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The first statement of the problem seeks to determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, and worker status. The results below show the results per category.

Figure 1. *Generational Distribution of the Respondents*

The figure above illustrates the distribution of respondents in terms of their generational group: Generation X and Generation Y. The figure shows that most respondents (81%) belonged to Generation Y. In comparison, the minority (19%) were part of Generation X. This result implies that most respondents are 27 to 42 years old. Meanwhile, the age bracket for those who make up the minority ranges from 43 to 58.

Figure 2. Sex Distribution of the Respondents

The sex distribution of the respondents is shown in Figure 5. As illustrated in the figure above, 53% of the respondents (with a frequency of 53) who answered the survey identified themselves as female. The remaining 47% (with a frequency of 47) identified themselves as male. The results imply that most respondents are biologically female, while the minority are biologically male.

Figure 3. Working Status of the Respondents

The figure above represents the respondents' distribution regarding their employment status in the university. As shown in the figure above, most of the faculty who answered the survey (58%) were already tenured, while those in the probationary period comprised the minority (4%) of the respondents. This result indicates that most respondents are

faculty members already tenured in the university while the minority are still in probationary status.

2. Perceived Ease of Use

The second statement of the problem attempts to investigate the significant difference in the level of influence perceived ease of use has between Generation X and Generation Y of the SHS faculty.

<i>E-wallets Perceived Ease of Use</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>IQR</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Alpha</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
<i>Gen X</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>.975</i>	<i>.05</i>	<i>Failed to Reject Ho</i>	<i>Not Significant</i>
<i>Gen Y</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>1</i>				

Table 1. *Perceived Ease of Use of Different Generational Groups*

The comparative analysis of the two generational groups regarding their perceived ease of use of e-wallets is revealed in Table 1. As shown in the results, with both Generation X and Y faculty having a median of 4 (IQR = 1), it is evident that both groups show the same level of homogeneous agreement when it comes to the ease of use of e-wallets. Furthermore, it is also found that there is no statistically different evidence to reject the null hypothesis ($p > .05$) as there is no significant difference between the respondents' perceived ease of use and their age using the 5% level of significance. These results imply that the SHS faculty of Generation X and Y are similar in their perceptions of e-wallets being easy to use.

3. Perceived Usefulness

The third statement of the problem aims to determine the significant differences in the level of influence Perceived Usefulness has between Generation X and Generation Y of the SHS faculty.

<i>E-wallets Usefulness</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>IQR</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Alpha</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
<i>Gen X</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>1.5</i>	<i>.594</i>	<i>.05</i>	<i>Failed to Reject Ho</i>	<i>Not Significant</i>
<i>Gen Y</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>2</i>				

Table 2. *Perceived Usefulness of Different Generational Groups*

The table above presents the two generational groups' comparative analysis according to their perceived usefulness towards e-wallets. As observed in the figure above, results revealed that both Generation X and Generation Y showed the same level of agreement on the perceived usefulness of e-wallet adoption, with both obtaining a median of 4. However, the results also indicate that the faculty of Generation X (IQR=1.5) showed more consistency in their responses than Generation Y (IQR=2), with the former having a lower interquartile range than the latter, implying more variability. Moreover, findings also revealed that there is no statistically significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis ($p > .05$), which may mean that there is no significant difference between their perceived usefulness and the age of the respondents using the 5% significance level. These results indicate that Generation X and Y of the SHS faculty have similar perceptions regarding the usefulness of e-wallets.

D. Social Influence

The fourth statement of the problem aims to investigate the significant differences in the level of social influence on Generation X and Generation Y of the SHS faculty when adopting e-wallets.

<i>E-wallets Social Influence</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>IQR</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Alpha</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
<i>Gen X</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>.625</i>	<i>.05</i>	<i>Failed to Reject Ho</i>	<i>Not Significant</i>
<i>Gen Y</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>2</i>				

Table 3. *Social Influence of Different Generational Groups*

The comparative analysis of the level of social influence on e-wallet adoption between Generation X and Generation Y is shown in Table 3. As seen in the table, it is found that both Generation X and Generation Y showed the same level of neutrality regarding the impact of social influence on their decision to adopt e-wallets, evident that both groups obtained a median of 3 (IQR=2). Furthermore, findings also show no statistically significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis ($p > .05$), indicating no significant difference between the respondents' perceived social influence and the generational group they belong to using a 5% significance level. This result implies that Generation X and Generation Y of the SHS faculty do not differ in their level of influence from social influence.

DISCUSSION

The Table 1 results are congruent with a previous study published by Hapsoro and Kismiatur (2022), who claimed that perceived ease of use does not differ in varying generational groups when adopting e-wallets.

The Table 2 findings also support the study conducted by Hapsoro and Kismiatur (2022), who claimed in their paper that the varying age groups hold no significant differences in their perceived usefulness towards e-wallets as they concluded that the level of influence perceived usefulness has on e-wallet adoption does not differ according to the generational category they belong.

Table 3 results on the other hand, concur with Chandra & Hartono's (2018) study, wherein they claimed that the influence of social influence among the different age groups has no significant differences, which implies that the level of social influence does not differ or vary according to the generational group the individual is.

The study has recapitulated the following key findings based on the results from the quantitative analysis discussed:

- (1) The Generation X and Generation Y faculty do not have any significant differences in their level of perceived ease of use towards e-wallets which indicates that this factor does not vary according to an individual's age group;
- (2) There is no significant difference in the level of perceived usefulness between the Generation X and Y faculty which may imply that their perception of e-wallets being easy to use does not vary according to the generational group they are in;
- (3) Lastly, the Generation X and Y faculty also do not differ significantly in terms of social influence as this result implies that the level of social influence is the same.

Conclusions

The following key conclusions were organized according to the order in which the statement of the problems was listed in the Introduction of the paper.

1. Is there a significant difference in the level of influence perceived ease of use has on the SHS Faculty Generation X and Generation Y in terms of their intention to adopt e-wallets?

As shown in the results, there was no statistically significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), as there was no significant difference between the respondents' perceived ease of use and their age using a 0.05 level of significance ($p > .05$). Therefore, the implications of these results indicate that adoption of e-wallets due to the influence of

perceived ease of use does not vary according to an individual's generational group such as Generation X and Y.

2. Is there a significant difference in the level of influence perceived usefulness has on the SHS Faculty Generation X and Generation Y in terms of their intention to adopt e-wallets?

Based on the results, there was no statistically significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis (Ho2). This is evident as there was no statistically significant evidence to deny it ($p > .05$), implying no significant difference between the respondents' perceived usefulness and their generational group. Therefore, their perception of adopting e-wallets according to their perceived usefulness does not vary according to their generation.

3. Is there a significant difference in the level of social influence on Generation X and Generation Y of the SHS Faculty regarding their intention to adopt e-wallets?

Results revealed that there was also no statistically significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis (Ho3), which could indicate that there is no significant difference between the respondents' social influence and the generational group they belong to using the 5% level of significance ($p > .05$). This could imply that their perception of adopting e-wallets according to social influence does not vary according to their age bracket.

The study's conclusion indicates that the level of perception of adopting e-wallets according to their ease of use, usefulness, and social influence does not vary among different generations like Generation X and Y. These findings seemingly point out that both Generation X and Y are equally affected by the three factors that influence e-wallet adoption, and not one has a more dominating influence than the other.

Recommendations

As this study revealed that Generation X and Y are affected equally by the three factors that influence the adoption of e-wallets, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. E-wallet developers should consider upgrading the navigation interface of e-wallet applications to be simpler and easier to use so that e-wallets will continue to appeal to plenty more users globally.
2. E-wallet developers should consider upgrading their e-wallet applications by adding additional features to increase their utility and usefulness.
3. E-wallet developers should promote the many utilities and benefits of e-wallets through advertisement to easily persuade the mass public to adopt them.
4. If future researchers wish to expand on this specific topic of study, a more extensive and diverse sample is recommended to yield more valid and accurate results.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Abiding by the Data Privacy Act of the Philippines 2012 provisions, the researchers ensured that all personal information and data were not disclosed to people outside the research group. The respondents were allowed to choose whether or not to place their names on the questionnaires. Furthermore, they were de-identified and anonymized by assigning code numbers.

The collected data were stored digitally inside the researchers' Google Drive and a backup universal serial bus (USB), as they will remain confidential only to the researchers. Data shall be disposed of three years after the research manuscript has been completed. The study results may be presented at a conference or published in an academic journal. However, the respondents' identities shall remain private and confidential.

Additionally, results from the data analysis were reported with no evidence of bias and manipulation. Lastly, the researchers obtained a permit to conduct the study from the Research Ethics Committee at their University.

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